

NOVEL 3D PREFORM ARCHITECTURE FOR PERFORMANCE AND RELIABILITY OF STRUCTURAL BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Beams are among the most frequently used structural members in constructions. Presently composite beams are not available wherein the web(s) have integrated fibre assemblies oriented in bias (+/-0°) directions relative to the beam's length direction, the flange/s have integrated fibre assemblies oriented in the beam's length and width (0°/90°) directions, and the web(s) - flange(s) have mutual through-thickness integrity at their junctions. Consequently, the competitive potential of composite beams is not fully utilised with respect to conventional counterparts built from isotropic materials. To overcome this shortcoming and bring composite beams to a new level of competitiveness, an innovative Add-on Weaving technique has been specifically developed recently. This Paper introduces the novel woven preform architecture and presents the initial results demonstrating the performance of new composite I-beams developed for the purpose. This advancement reflects maturing of the new weaving technique and its 3D fabric reinforcements and also supports its transit from lab to industry.

1 INTRODUCTION

Beams with cross-sectional forms like e.g. I, T and U are used in a variety of constructions. Most beams are designed for mechanical performance based on cross-sectional shapes that are relatively easy to produce from metals and assuming isotropic material properties. The functional aspect, is thus governed and limited by restrictions related to the choice of material and established production methods for these materials. Composite materials have to some extent successfully replaced metal beams in certain applications and are then also used to make more unconventional cross sections, e.g. Π -profiles. However, although composites can bring about new beam cross section shapes and anisotropic material properties they are also hampered by being built from 2D reinforcement, typically in the form of laminates. The inability to engineer beams together with mechanical performance and functional reliability explains to some extent why such beams are not yet competitive at the level of their full potential.

The distinction between performance and reliability is made on the basis that performance is governed by orientation of fibres in load bearing paths, and reliability by the level/degree and positions/locations of integration in the whole structure. Stacking fibres in multi-directional plies would give improved performance but without their being sufficiently integrated in proper places/positions there is risk for delamination and hence premature material failure, i.e. low reliability.

Much effort has been spent over the years in developing different constructs of beams. Figure 1 below shows the pultrusion and lamination approaches through representation of a T cross-section.

While these beams could be suitable for many simple applications, they cannot be considered in applications where high material performance and reliability are required, for example in buildings, aircraft, vehicles etc. New textile technologies combining fibres oriented in 3D could help solving these problems and advancing the field of composites further.

Figure 1: Constructs of T-beams by pultrusion and lamination methods.

Most beams consist of combinations of flanges and webs. While in use, the flanges are largely loaded in longitudinal axial tension/compression and the webs primarily in shear, although they are also sometimes partly loaded in transverse compression and tension. Thus, such beams ought to have high tensile/compressive strength in the flanges and predominantly high shear strength in the web. This is of course achievable by incorporating fibres suitably oriented in required directions. However, for the beam to function reliably, a mutual through-thickness integration of the flange/s and web/s is imperative. Hence, a novel fabric-forming process, Add-on Weaving, has been developed recently to enable production of more efficient composite beams than can be obtained with existing reinforcement architectures.

2 DRAWBACKS OF PRESENT PRACTICE

Beams of many different cross-sections are produced today by what could be categorized as indirect method. Fabric sheets, or prepregs, are cut, stacked in different orientations and folded/formed into desired shapes. Possibly the stacked fabrics are stitched through, at least in some places, to enable their handling for subsequent infusion and consolidation. As shown in Fig. 2, such plied construction produces longitudinal channels with triangular cross sections at web-flange junctions. Unless such channels are filled with something else they will fill up with pure resin during infiltration/consolidation. Usually that is avoided by filling the hollow with fibres in the form of tows, rovings, twisted fabrics etc. and at other times using ‘noodles’ or ‘fillers’, which are integrated structures, sometimes having shape and dimensions close to the triangular hollow that they fill.

Figure 2: Stacking and draping fibres and/or fabrics to create corners in a profiled beam generates a hollow where a web and flange meet.

However, due to the sharp out-of-plane bends of the plies between the web(s) and flange(s), the load paths between them is not as efficient as one would like. In contrary, a very weak joint is created at the region which is most critical for load transfer. The tows, noodles, fillers etc. put in the triangular hollow do not significantly contribute in improving the load transfer between the flanges and the web although they help reducing the risk for crack initiation that might otherwise easily occur if the triangular hollow was only filled with matrix. Composite materials comprising such fabric reinforcement constructions are thus vulnerable to delamination, i.e. failure by cracking and splitting. Apparently the laminated materials are not optimal for high-performance applications.

When looking at introduction of composite beams in heavy-duty applications, their walls would naturally become thicker than in their metal counterparts. In addition the slenderness of the beams might become a challenge in production if conventional 2D fabrics are used in their assembly. The traditional laminating methods used in composite manufacturing might therefore not be feasible for large volume production of composite beams and more continuous production methods would then be desired. In the case of laminated assemblies, regardless of if the beam's walls are relatively thinner or thicker, joining them by stitches, staples, pins etc. to increase their handling integrity and/or reducing the risk for in-service delamination is typically associated with increased costs.

3 PAST ATTEMPTS

Some alternative ways, other than stitching, have been attempted at in the past three decades to address delamination problems. These methods may be categorized as direct and could be exemplified through those developed by Kohtaro [1], Bompard and Lamarie [2], Edgson and Temple [3] etc. However, these methods also do not provide satisfactory and reliable 3D fabric reinforcements because they have some important shortcomings. For example, webs and flanges do not comprise one or more walls/layers of structurally integrated yarns in $\pm \theta^\circ$ orientations and/or in $0^\circ/90^\circ$ orientations respectively and there is no mutual through-thickness integration between the webs and flanges. As a result, the products of these methods also suffer from lack of features necessary for optimal performance and reliability and hence have not been useful. Also, the methods are not practicable.

Figure 3: Attempts in the past to develop methods for producing I-beams have not been practical resulting in unsatisfactory reinforcement structures: (a) Kohtaro (1984), (b) Bompard and Lamarie (1986) and (c) Edgson and Temple (1991).

As can be understood now from the foregoing presentation, the presently available methods are inefficient and impracticable for producing truly advanced and complex 3D fabric items meeting increasing requirements on mechanical performance, functional reliability and cost effectiveness of emerging high-performance composite materials.

4 SOME RELEVANT ASPECTS OF I-BEAM

It is relevant at this point to consider some aspects of an I-beam to understand its technical and economic requirements and use them as a basis for engineering suitable textile reinforcements.

An I-beam consists of two parallel (horizontal) flanges separated by a (vertical) web. The flanges are loaded in axial tension/compression while the web is primarily loaded in shear, and partly also in transverse compression and tension between the flanges. Ideally high tensile/compressive strength in the flanges and predominantly high shear strength in the web are desirable.

Standardized metal I-beam profiles have cross sections that have been optimized to fulfil these requirements, partly also taking stability aspects into account such as local buckling of the flanges during bending. That optimization has however been performed under the assumption that the beam material is isotropic which is the case for steel and other metals.

Fibre reinforced composites are primarily potentially much stronger and stiffer than metals in relation to their weight. But another aspect that makes them even more competitive to metals is that they can be made anisotropic by controlling the fibre orientations according to performance requirements. This way their strength and stiffness are aligned with the directions of the applied loads, not only by optimizing the geometry but also the material properties.

Composite materials are generally considered to be brittle and thus lacking the ductility of metal that is sometimes regarded as a "safety margin" or a potential "warning signal" in the event of overload or other unforeseen hazardous events. However, both wood and concrete are also brittle materials and therefore brittleness of composites do not by any means disqualify them from infrastructure applications.

Not many composite beams are used in civil engineering today. The first reason for this absence is that most fibre reinforced composites are typically relatively expensive compared to traditional construction materials. If the structural weight is not an issue then there is little incentive to introduce composites unless other benefits of the material are identified, e.g. fatigue properties, low electrical conductivity or ability to cope with corrosive environments. Secondly there are well-established codes for utilizing, e.g. steel and concrete in civil engineering while there is virtually no such codes for fibre reinforced composites. However, an effort is currently being made to expand the Eurocode to also include guidelines for fibre composite materials. It will obviously take some time until such codes have matured and harmonized to the level of existing codes for more established construction materials.

The "maturity" of composite beams is primarily a matter of willingness, market and need, notwithstanding there are still some challenges to address. Looking at the broader picture of I-beams in particular, there are some important factors apart from availability and cost that hampers introduction of fibre reinforced composites on a larger scale. These include aspects like joining and assembly, and manufacturing of textile profiled beams, which are discussed in some detail below.

4.1 Joining and assembly

End users of metal beams are used to welding or bolting them together. While welding in conventional sense is ruled out for CFRP beams, bolting may not be optimal. The potential benefits of introducing CFRP beams in constructions could be significantly reduced if the performance of the joints is lower than that of the beams. Composite beams could be welded if its matrix is thermoplastic. For thermosetting polymers some kind of bonding operation would be required. In principle bolting would work equally well for composite beams as for metal beams. However,

generally the use of mechanical fasteners in composites is considered unfavourable because the metal joining elements either drive up the weight or render the joints considerably weaker than the joined members. Depending on service temperature, use of metallic joints could pose problems with composites due to thermal incompatibility.

In many (well designed) constructions today, the main load transfer may not take place in areas where there are joints, or at least not with the main load being transferred straight through the joining elements. Hence, it is not obvious that such joints would cause considerable problems for the concept. For instance, if beams are standing on top of other beams in a framework the fasteners are primarily there for fixing with relatively lower load requirements. It could be safely assumed that joining is an essential aspect of the CFRP beam concept but not an obvious show stopper. With new composite joining element solutions being developed to solve most of the mentioned problems, joining of composite beams could be achieved well.

4.2 Manufacturing textile profiled beams

There are a couple of main concerns when trying to produce shapes such as I-beams with composite materials. For most of the existing composites, the fibre reinforcements come in various forms of 2D sheet-like materials such as woven fabrics, prepregs, mats or non-crimp fabrics. In order to build a three-dimensionally shaped component like a profiled beam, the fibrous sheet-like materials have to be cut, folded, draped and somehow fixated to create a stacked/layered/plied assembly for subsequent handling and infusing/consolidating of the matrix material.

As mentioned above the structural function of an I-beam is that it generates excellent bending stiffness and strength by separating two flanges a certain distance apart so that they become loaded almost purely in evenly distributed tension and compression. The same principle is utilized in trusses and sandwich structures, and common for them all is that the material between the parts loaded in tension/compression needs to maintain the distance and ensure that the opposing parts interact mechanically. That requires the materials to be strong in shear and also be able to withstand some compression. Another requirement is that web-flanges interfaces should be strong and provide good structural integrity.

For composite beams one would ideally like to have the reinforcement in the flanges predominantly oriented in the axial direction of the beam. (For practical reasons some transverse reinforcement is also desired since composites with only unidirectional reinforcement tend to become fragile in the transverse direction.) In the web $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation of the fibres would typically be preferred and, apparently, that in combination with the 0° orientation in the flanges is difficult to obtain with an efficient load transfer between the flanges and the web, employing established techniques.

In addition to the different fibre orientation requirements on the web and flanges, forming beams with sheet-like laminar reinforcement introduces another problem. The reinforcement in the web needs to be split and folded apart to generate interfaces with the flanges. Such splitting and folding of reinforcement from the web to connect to the flanges is quite unfavourable from a load transfer point of view. An illustration of a typical laminar architecture for a T-beam is presented in Fig. 2 where it is obvious that the layers in the web will be brought into the flanges, but more importantly the created hollow makes the load paths locally at the web-flange junction discontinuous and a very weak area is formed just in the region that is most critical for the load transfer. This adversely affects the functional reliability of the beam.

5 LATEST ADVANCEMENT

With a view to overcome the above-discussed shortcomings of the presently available profiled beams, a new weaving technique, called Add-on Weaving, has been developed. Through it 3D fabric beams, and many other relatively complex object-like preforms, are directly obtainable. The produced reinforcement beams uniquely combine structurally integrated yarns in $\pm 45^\circ$ orientations in webs and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ orientations in flanges, with mutual through-thickness integration of the web-flange junctions.

Fig. 4 illustrates schematically a profiled beam having I cross-section. In addition to engineering the much required performance and reliability, the Add-on Weaving process is beneficial in that the entire profiled 3D fabric preform is produced directly in one step in net shape and virtually without generating scrap. The new weaving process and its products are thus technically and economically relevant.

Figure 4: The novel Add-on Weaving method uniquely engineers performance and reliability in profiled beams by incorporating structurally integrated fibres in $\pm 45^\circ$ orientations in webs and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ orientations in flanges, and mutual through-thickness integration of web-flange junctions.

With the demonstration of the newly developed Add-on Weaving technology completed, it is now ready to move from lab to industry. The main challenge now is to improve the production rate through development of weaving machines dedicated for producing specific items. This way the extra features and functions in the machine to accord production flexibility are minimized or avoided. Such weaving machines then produce only specific products. With fewer and lighter moving parts in the machine the production rate can be directly increased. Through Add-on Weaving technology many novel 3D fabric products are producible and they are considered to be suitable solutions for a variety of industrial applications. Tests conducted on some of the materials have established their high-performance and reliability. One such product developed is the I-beam presented here. The first results of tests performed on this I-beam are presented here after providing its relevant constructional aspects.

5.1 Constructional aspects of new I-beam

Carbon fibre I-beam preforms similar to the one illustrated in Fig. 4 were produced employing the Add-on Weaving technology. To enable comparison, an IPE 80 S2775JR steel beam was chosen as reference with the relevant dimensions indicated in Table 1. Each of the woven beam's flanges consisted of four layers of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ woven fabrics, with the 0° (warp) direction coinciding with the beam's longitudinal direction. The weave was unbalanced with a majority of the fibres in the 0° direction. The webs primarily contained four layers of integrated $\pm 45^\circ$ oriented fibres and two layers of integrated $0^\circ/90^\circ$ reinforcement. The two innermost layers in the webs were $0^\circ/90^\circ$ layers and they extended out, through one of the flanges, where they were folded out on top of that flange. Through this "design" the web had two layers of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ orientated fibre reinforcement layers in addition to four layers of $\pm 45^\circ$ oriented fibres. One of the flanges was given some extra reinforcement because the strength in compression typically is lower than in tension for CFRP materials. A principal illustration

of the cross section of the wholly unified 3D-assembled I-beam preform is shown in Fig. 5. The carbon fibre preforms were infused with epoxy through resin transfer moulding.

Figure 5: Architecture of the 3D-assembled I-beam preform. Inset photo shows the mutual through-thickness integration between fibre bundles in the web the flange.

6 ANALYSIS

There are several ways to compare beams of different materials and regardless of how it is done some measures need to be compromised. In this study the aim was to keep the cross-sectional shape, i.e. both the outer dimensions and the web and flange thicknesses, close to that of the reference steel beam. The final dimensions of the composite beams varied somewhat since the production was made on a prototype Add-on Weaving machine. Data for the steel and composite beams are presented in Table 1. The composite beams weighed approximately 1.2 kg/m, which was only 1/5 of the weight of the reference steel beams.

Material	h (mm)	b (mm)	t_f	t_w	A (mm)	Weight (kg/m)
Steel	80	40	5.2	3.8	764	6
3D- CFRP	81	41	4.6	4.6	710	1.2

Table 1: Beam data

The CFRP I-beam and its steel reference were evaluated in a 4-point bending test illustrated in Fig. 6. The test set-up was suited for comparing beam properties in bending and by adjustment of the measures L_1 and L_2 the ratio between the maximum bending moment and the maximum shear force could be controlled. Thus both the maximum bending moment and the maximum shear force that the beam could withstand could be tested in the same load case, with the possibility of maintaining in the rig the necessary ratios between the support distances L_1 and L_2 indicated in Fig. 6.

According to analytical estimates the transition from shear failure to tensile/compressive failure happens at a support distance difference $L_1 - L_2 = 253$ mm, implying that it would be hard to obtain shear failure in the beam. Since the load pads in the test rig were about 100 mm wide there would virtually not be any free span between the load points at that support distance. Based on the analysis it was decided to use span lengths $L_1 = 900$ mm and $L_2 = 225$ mm in the comparative bending tests and then alter the lengths depending on the outcome of the first tests.

Figure 6: A schematic illustration of the 4-point bending test used in the study.

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7 EXPERIMENTAL

The 4-point bending tests were performed in an Instron universal test machine. The load and displacement were recorded using a 100 kN load cell and displacement data from the test machine. The experiments were conducted at a constant deformation rate of 5 mm per min between the inner and outer load points. A photograph of the test rig is presented in Fig. 7. Two steel beams and two CFRP beams were tested using the support lengths presented in Table 2.

Figure 7. A steel beam in the 4-point test rig used in the experiments

Beam	L_1	L_2
S1	900	225
C1	900	225
S2	510	225
C2	510	225

Table 2. Test beams: steel (S) and composite (C)

8 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results from the two initial bending tests (beams S1 and C1) are presented in Fig. 8. Apparently the composite beam is neither as stiff nor as strong as the steel beam. However, it should be noted that the steel beam is 5 times heavier than the composite beam and there are some other interesting aspects of these results, which are discussed in the following.

Figure 8. Load vs. displacement graphs for beams S1 and C1.

The maximum load for the steel I-beam occurs after a linear response at about 6 mm displacement, implying that the beam would have collapsed if the load was maintained or increased further. The composite beam also shows an initial linear response before damage is initiated but after damage initiation the load still increases with increasing displacement and the maximum load occurs after about 24 mm displacement. It should be noted that the deflection of the beam is considerably greater since the recorded displacement is between the inner and outer load points in the rig.

Apparently the composite beam displays a seemingly ductile load-displacement behaviour although it is made from brittle materials. This means that the structural response resembles that of a metal beam rather than that of e.g. wood or concrete, or for that matter what is usually expected from a CFRP beam. This type of response is likely related to the mutual through-thickness integrity of the reinforcement at the intersection between the flanges and the web, which suppresses delamination once damage has initiated. The damage then grows progressively and in a stable manner and does not cause immediate brittle failure. Fig. 9 illustrates the failure in the CFRP I-beam, showing multiple compressive failures in the flange.

Figure 9. Beam C1 with multiple compressive damages in the compressed flange that occurred before the beam finally failed completely.

It should however be noted that at about 27 mm displacement the composite beam had failed completely while the steel beam still deformed plastically. Due to large deformations and severe misalignment of the rig, coming from skewed bending of the beam, the test of the steel beam was interrupted after about 28 mm displacement. When the composite beam failed it had absorbed about half as much energy as the steel beam.

In Fig. 10 the load vs. displacement results have been normalised with the weight of the beams. As can be noticed the composite beam then outperforms the steel beam both in stiffness, strength and absorbed energy. The relative stiffness is only marginally higher but the relative strength and energy absorption is about 2.9 times and 2.4 times higher, respectively.

Figure 10. Load per beam weight vs. displacement graphs for beams S1 and C1

In a second round of tests the outer support length was reduced to $L1 = 510$ mm. The results are presented in Fig. 11. This test was aimed at obtaining shear failure in the beams but for the steel beam that never occurred since the beam again underwent skew bending in an unstable manner. The composite beam also deformed in a combination of bending and twist and the loading was interrupted relatively early for both beams.

Figure 11. Load vs. displacement graphs for beams S2 and C2

The ratio between the maximum loads for the steel and CFRP beams was similar in the second test as in the first, although the loads were a5% higher. The loading was interrupted at 8-9 mm displacement between the load points. The results for the tested beams are summarised in Table 3.

Beam	L₁ (mm)	Max Load (kN)	Rel. max load (kN/kg)	Energy abs. (kJ)	Rel. energy abs. (kJ/kg)
S1	4	40.1	6.68	894	149
C1	4	22.9	19.1	426	355
S2	2.27	67.4	11.2	368	61.4
C2	2.27	37.3	31.1	197	165

Table 3. Results from the mechanical tests on I-beams

9 CONCLUSIONS

The 3D CFRP I-beam's mechanical performance is exceptionally good compared with the steel beams. Looking at their relative properties, i.e. properties normalised with weight, they have similar stiffness but 2-3 times better strength and energy absorption. The CFRP beams are 1/5 the weight of steel beams.

The 3D CFRP I-beams uniquely demonstrate a quasi-ductile failure with a significant remaining load carrying capacity after initial failure. That is not common for CFRP materials and can likely be attributed to the mutual through-thickness integrity of the flanges and the webs of the textile reinforcement beams.

The Add-on Weaving process' ability to engineer mechanical performance and functional reliability in 3D textile reinforcements is established and it can transit from lab to industry. Its development opens new opportunities in advancing composite materials and its fields of applications.

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